

RISKS EXISTING IN SMALL BUSINESS OF GEORGIA AND THEIR REDUCTION MECHANISMS**Vekua D.,***Doctor of Economics,
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Supporting small business in Georgia on the way to European integration is one of the important vectors of economic policy.

In the conditions of globalization, with limited financial resources and a limited area of activity, small businesses have become much more sensitive to risks. In a number of cases, as a result of ineffective risk management in Georgia, the liquidity of assets and the amount of capital of small business enterprises are significantly reduced, risks are not properly managed, and small enterprises go bankrupt or receive significant losses.

The article discusses and analyzes the risks that hinder development of small business in Georgia. It is proposed to establish a modern system of risk insurance, of which will be possible to reduce losses caused by damage in small businesses.

Keywords: small business, medium-sized business, risks, loss, insurance.

Supporting small businesses on the way to European integration is one of the important vectors of economic policy in Georgia. Promotion policy of small business should ensure growth of the economic potential of the country, overcoming existing social poverty, improving business environment and rapid implementation of innovations in the economy.

According to the 2020 data of the National Statistical Service of Georgia, "Compared to 2015, the turnover of small and medium-sized businesses was increased almost twice, in the same period, the share of small and medium-sized businesses in the total turnover was 41%, while in 2015 it was only 18.1%." [1]. However, if we analyze the sectoral structure of small businesses in Georgia, we will see that almost half of the turnover comes from trading and car repairing, which is caused by lack of opportunities for the production of innovative products and by less creative initiatives.

Along with the increasing of production capacity of small and medium-sized businesses in Georgia, the capital structure of small and medium-sized enterprises is also changing significantly. According to the data of the same service, "if in 2015 their share in the total capital structure was 13.2%, in 2020 it was increased to 51.8%" [2]. Which should be undeniably considered as a positive process, although the products and services provided by the majority of these small and medium-sized enterprises are still far from modern quality standards.

The current globalization process has essentially changed the business environment, its territorial and sectoral structure. These changes were reflected in all aspects of economic relations of small and medium-sized businesses. With limited area of activity and financial resources, small businesses became much more sensitive to risks. As a result of ineffective risk man-

agement, the liquidity of assets and the amount of capital of small business enterprises are significantly reduced.

Small enterprises do not have the opportunity to have a special risk management service or a specialists engaged in this work, due to which risks are not properly managed and small enterprises go bankrupt or receive significant losses.

Risks that are directly related to the economic activity of a small enterprises belong to the category of internal risks. "The realization of this category of risks can be provoked by lack of capital, low liquidity of assets, change of price policy, limitation of marketing measures and etc." [3]. All these possible risks are typical for small businesses in Georgia, and therefore small business management should pay special attention to the management of internal financial risks. Financial risks can be conventionally grouped into two types: "risks related to the purchasing power of money and risks related to investments and capital investment". Purchasing power risks include: inflation, currency risks, asset liquidity risks and etc., but risks associated with capital devaluation and failure to receive expected profit can be attributed to investment risks" [4].

Small businesses, unlike other business entities, are especially vulnerable during financial crises, but it can also (due to its small scale) quickly regenerate and actively influence on the recovery and development of the economy. In order for the successful generation process of small businesses in Georgia, investors who are interested in such businesses need to be reliable and their investments should be diversified.

External risks of small business include: social-economic, environmental change, natural and ecological cataclysms and frequent changes in state regulations. It is clear that small enterprises have much less opportunities to influence such risks, however, these risks must be taken into account when making business

plans and defining perspectives. Due to the variety of risks, in small and medium-sized enterprises, the necessity of risk management should be evaluated according to the economic loss. Despite the frequency of risks, if the volume of losses caused by this risk is insignificant, it is possible to ignore them.

The growth of the innovative potential of small enterprises and the improvement of the quality of released products in Georgia is the most important for not only to meet increased demand of the population of Georgia to these products, but also to increase potential of export of the country. The lack of a correct management strategy for innovative risks in small and medium-sized enterprises of Georgia is often one of the factors that reduce the inflow of venture capital and hinders the growth of competitiveness of such enterprises and the development of their future potential.

Small and medium-sized enterprises are also highly sensitive to reputational risks. The loss or damage of reputation directly effects on their economic situation, because of the high competition at the market. Like the famous Georgian proverb says, "it is better to break the head than to break the name".

The expansion and concentration of modern business has put small and medium-sized businesses in front of a new challenges and risks. These challenges and risks relate to the growing trend of merger of small businesses by large businesses, motivated by the desire to increase assets, improve capital structure and monopolize the business.

Small businesses cannot deal with these challenges on their own in Georgia. First of all, substantial support from the state is needed, which is primarily related to the improvement of the business environment for small businesses. The improvement should affect taxation regimes, state regulation mechanisms, attraction of investments, start-ups, innovative activities and etc. Creative people should be given more financial opportunities for startups and innovative activities. State grants, small business co-financing system and etc. should be used for this purpose.

Along with the development of small business, increases the volume of its capital and therefore increases such business risks which are connected with devaluation or damage of capital. Natural events such as: earthquake, flood, heavy snowfall, storm, hail and etc. should be considered like risks mentioned above. There may also be danger in the small business workspace, for example fire or explosion may occur.

It is possible for a business to be damaged by leaking water from plumbing and drainage systems, leaking liquids such as water, oil, petroleum, etc. from boilers or pipes. There are risks that criminal activities such as theft, robbery and vandalism can also have a negative impact on small business operations.

The existence of all the above-mentioned business risks leads to the need to manage them. Small business owners can use a financial tool of risk management, such as insurance.

Unfortunately, in Georgia, many representatives of small businesses do not have experience and proper information about the use and need of insurance services. They do not have proper financial education and do not know that there are many different small business insurance products available. They need to understand that the amount paid to purchase an insurance policy is a payment for secure future and will compensate losses caused by damages occurred while operating a small business. It is necessary to implement the tradition of insurance of small business risks in Georgia, which has been actively used in Western economies for many years.

By insurance for small business, an entrepreneur will protect the property his business owns, the health of his business employees, and he will also be protected from expenses caused by damage to other people's property and health due to his own fault.

In the insurance companies operating on the insurance market of Georgia, list of insurance products required for entrepreneurs employed in small businesses should preferably look like this: property insurance, transportation insurance, cargo insurance, construction risks insurance, agro insurance, business interruption insurance, financial risks insurance, third party liability insurance, health, life and personal accident insurance for employees.

From the point of view of reducing risks in small businesses in Georgia, it is undoubtedly a positive process to use the experience of family activities in traditional businesses, because behind the experience of managing such businesses there are many years and sometimes even centuries. Also, the experience of the European Union in managing small businesses will undoubtedly help to prevent risks.

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